

TARGETED MESSAGING ABOUT FOOD STORAGE IN SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS

by

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Targeted Messaging about Food Storage in Social Media Posts

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Abstract— With current global food waste rates being at an extreme, the question arises of how do restaurateurs, particularly ones searching for the perfect Instagram picture to post, contribute to global food waste? The problem is more relevant now, seeing that users are so focused on trying the trendiest foods, however not realizing the amount of food they waste. The solution to this is to educate the users about ways that they may be able to store their leftovers to be consumed at a later time. This research project aims at creating a machine learning program using Python and Microsoft Computer Vision in order to process Instagram pictures and Twitter Tweets. The machine learning program will determine the food presented in the post and display an informational message on how that food can be stored for later consumption. A dataset, provided and published by the U.S. Department of Agriculture, contains a variety of foods and ways those can be stored through three main means: pantry, refrigeration, and freezing. The method of this research project included reading twitter Tweets as well as processing Instagram images to determine what food was being displayed or talked about. The program then analyzed the dataset and recognized the food item. If the food was present in the dataset, the program displayed leftover storage options. As a result, the program accurately found and identified the food from the images and Tweets. The impact of our findings informs users on Instagram and Twitter on ways to preserve leftovers. This ultimately reduces food waste. Our hope is that these results cause social media users to consider how their actions might impact society negatively and how we can use technology to solve societal problems.

Index Terms— machine learning, Instagram, Twitter, food waste, artificial intelligence,

programming languages, Python, FoodKeeper, sustainability, food safety

I. INTRODUCTION

Food waste is a major prevalent issue circulating in modern society. It is vital to examine the impacts and the reasons for the contributions towards this growing waste. Studies have shown that 30 to 40 percent of all food supply in just the United States is wasted [1]. This amounts to approximately 133 billion pounds. On a global scale this percent would be much higher. Implications of food waste are substantial in that they encompass effects on health, food marketing, climate change, as well as food security. On top of this the waste goes beyond just food, it entails wasted land, water, labor, and energy. The waste also contributes to waste in personal expenses as well. Annually, around \$240 billion worth of food is wasted, and this number broken down further results in about \$1,866 per year in the average household.

Another study finds that nearly 32% of the food that an average household purchases is wasted [2]. The questions here lies within the reason as to why this much food is discarded. A third study reveals that more than 80 percent of Americans prematurely discard food because of date label confusion [3]. Furthermore, it is important to dwell upon the idea that not all food is directly discarded to trash. There are sustainable practices that the U.S. attempts to implement to regain nutrition. However, with this comes different consequences. A report by Natural Resources Defense Council, Inc. specifies that the amount of energy that is utilized is around 16 percent in the U.S. alone related to food and agriculture [4]. This truly goes to show that even though sustainable practices have been incorporated to bypass some of the

waste that is created, everything still comes with a cost no matter how much we try to avoid it.

With the emergence of social media, the increase of individual platforms such as fashion and food blogs have grown exponentially. Specifically with food blogs, the importance of food waste and how it affects us globally comes into play. A great number of people post the food that they purchase from restaurants on social media platforms, such as Instagram and Twitter, as a way to share what they have been up to. Oftentimes these social media users will also rate and recommend places after they are done eating the items that they have posted. What is not shared on social media, is what happens to the food after. Will users consume all of the food that they have purchased? Will the food that is leftover be taken home to eat at a later time? Will the food that is leftover be thrown away, contributing to the large food waste that exists globally, and more specifically in the United States?

The aim of this thesis is to discover if there is a way, through machine learning, text processing, and artificial intelligence, to develop a program that will identify the food that a person is posting about on Twitter and Instagram and provide information on sustainable food storage and tips publicly. This would allow for users to reduce food waste in the world and increase awareness of the situation globally. The idea of reducing food waste through providing informational sections on Instagram posts and Twitter will be investigated through the development of a computer program written in Python that will implement machine learning algorithms in order to self-identify the food that is being pictured through the help of the plain text Tweets and Instagram posts.

A clear example of functionality similar to the one that is planned on being researched, is the information sections that Instagram has worked on to spread awareness about the COVID-19 situation. Their algorithm will catch a keyword that is posted to their platform concerning the global pandemic and will then create a small button at the bottom of a story screen that a user can click on. This link directs users to an external site that will then provide information on the current status of the pandemic, vaccines, and the CDC website [5]. This has helped spread awareness concerning situations about the pandemic, and the

sources that Instagram directs its users to is always a trusted source where users can rest assured.

One research objective that stems from my research aim is to use an artificial intelligence function that will be able to process an Instagram post to determine the food that is being posted or shared to their followers. In this research, Microsoft Computer Vision is the main function of artificial intelligence used to determine and describe the food images that are being posted to specifically Instagram. This objective would aim to solve and provide results of the research question posed concerning the ways that global food waste can be reduced, and awareness can be spread. This would be considered more of a short-term objective, considering that the informational section can be posted shortly after someone posts something food related on their Instagram account. It will take further research to implement and test in order for the algorithm to function correctly. The machine learning algorithm will take some time to process and learn the correct food to display information about.

One benefit that my research objective will bring is to increase awareness of how often we waste a great portion of food without realization. Many of us are so focused on posting about food places, that it facilitates the increase of other people following the trend and doing the same. Being focused on social media platforms and being concerned for how perfect the picture is taken, takes away focus from the food itself and dissolves any ounce of mindfulness when considering leftover food. By posting informational sections, similar to how Instagram is doing with Covid-19, people will take into consideration the ways that they can use leftovers, or how long some type of food can last, and how to properly store the leftovers. This helps restore the sense of mindfulness that the public forgets when being solely focused on posting and following the newest trends. The result of the study helps the bigger picture of resolving global food waste which has several different implications on our planet. A simple small action, such as this, can have a great impact when a greater number of people contribute to a cause for the betterment of society. With a great number of times spent on social media by users, it is vital to take into consideration and spread awareness about mindfulness and how even small

steps from us as a public can either have a positive or negative impact on society.

II. RELATED WORK

A great number of studies have found that social media influences the actions and thoughts of users. Specifically, food safety and preservation were amongst the matters that social networking platforms have affected.

Mou and Lin [6] took a deeper dive into the Chinese microblog platform Weibo used by the public to test users' responses to a series of food safety crises. Cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses were taken from a sample of 1,360 adults using the platform. The study concluded that a stronger predictor of perception of food safety risk and preventive action was found through emotional response in regards to the growing food safety incidents in China. This study goes to show the idea that social media can contribute to a behavioral and emotional effect on its users.

In a similar study, Mou [7] discusses social media networking sites and their role in food safety communication. The concept of risk communication is brought to light throughout the work. The World Health Organization [8] defines this term as the exchange of information, advice, and opinions in real-time to be discussed between officials and experts in matters that may impact people facing a hazard or threat to survival, health, or economic and social well-being. With the rise of social media, people do not have to solely rely on means of traditional media to access information. Mou uses a web survey and content analysis as two methodologies to examine the new risk communication pattern influenced by social networking platforms. Her conclusions found that further research would need to be conducted in order to provide more definitive results on the understanding of social capital throughout other cultural contexts, not just China.

Furthermore, Overbey, Jaykus, and Chapman [9] conducted a literature review analyzing several different studies focused on best ways to utilize social media to communicate food safety risks. The study found that best practices for social media were inconsistent, and the designs used within the study were greatly variable. The authors additionally

concluded that more effective guidelines for social media usage in delivering information concerning food safety and infectious disease risk need to be established.

Throughout these studies the common theme is prevention of foodborne illnesses and educating the public about food safety through means of social media and analyzing the effectiveness of doing so. This relates to my current research; however, these studies do not cover ways that there are proper ways for users to store food to keep them from perishing. That can be done so by educating the users on these various global platforms, as this research aims to do.

In a study conducted by Sutinen and Närvänen [10], the participation by market actors concerning the food waste issue with social media, considered to be a socio-cultural construction. The approach used within this study was to combine discourse analysis and netnography. Netnography[11] takes the traditional approach of ethnographic techniques and adapts it to the study of social media. It is an interpretive and qualitative research approach. The research emphasized the burden of understanding what is referred to as "discourses of complex sustainability issues" and the role that social marketing does play in either transforming or maintaining these discourses.

Moreover, Närvänen et al. [12] was a qualitative study that looked at the idea that the root of most food wasted in already developed countries is households. Through the use of online materials and interviews, the study was able to dive deeper deriving the connection between social media campaigns creating a positive sociocultural meaning when it came to food waste. It was determined that increasing consumer to consumer communications and by creating an atmosphere of positive meanings of food waste that resonate with the consumers were both ways to potentially address sustainability issues.

A study conducted by Jenkins, Brennan, Molenaar, McCaffery [13] aimed at examining how social media is currently being used as a tool in campaigns due to concerns of growing consumer food waste. The question of whether it was an effective communication tool was also discussed. It was found that out of the seventeen studies explored, in eleven of them there was a positive correlation between social media and

impact on users. An example, provided by the authors, included raising awareness on the contribution of food waste by consumers and the actions of reducing the issue. An important note to make is that conclusions also found that interventions which used other means of campaigning in addition to social media were found to be more effective in creating change to consumer behavior and increasing understanding of the global issue at hand.

As several previous studies have suggested, social media tends to influence users' behaviors across different platforms. Young et al. [14], in particular, took a look at three inventions that delivered messages to encourage reductions in food waste. A retailer's Facebook page, e-newsletter, and a retailer's magazine was utilized to derive conclusions. Although genuine face-to-face interaction cannot be replicated by social media and digital resources, the study found that the three means of intervention showed signs of significant reductions in the self-reported food waste throughout the duration of the study by customers.

In response to the previous study mentioned, Grainger et al. [15] was a study that aimed at dispelling the claim that Young et al. [14] made about face-to-face interaction in interventions not being able to be replicated by social media. It was decided that this statement was prematurely made without considering the major weight of knowledge accumulated in behavior change literature in the medical and psychology fields. Suggesting that Young et al. demonstrated the importance of evidence synthesis, the study claims that only one small piece of the puzzle is provided through the small sample of people and non-targeted intervention based off of the previous study discussed.

As seen in all of the studies discussed within this section, there are several related conclusions that suggest that there is a positive correlation between social media platforms and the global issue of food waste. Whether the impact of the platforms is small or large, the main takeaway is that the use of networking sites to combat the issue at hand is a valid and effective approach. Studies discussed in this section included counties outside of the U.S. to reinforce the idea that this issue is widespread on a global scale. It also goes to show the uniqueness of the present research discussed within this paper. There ceases to be a

presence of ways that food sustainability information, tips, and storage advice can be communicated or displayed to users on several applications.

III. DATASETS

Several datasets were analyzed and utilized within this research to ensure effective and accurate results.

A. Twitter Dataset

The TWINT scraper was used to obtain Tweets from January 1st, 2017, to January 1st, 2020, and Tweets that were marked as English translation were utilized only. Since this project is focused on the food waste in the United States, it was reasonable to use Tweets that are in the main language spoken in the country. Keywords were specified within the search in order to get Tweets related to food. In this situation it was appropriate to search for specific hashtags in Tweets that were relevant in order to get Tweets that would thoroughly be able to put the code to the test to pick up food entities. Relevant hashtags placed in the parameter for TWINT included: '#foodwaste', '#zerowaste', '#sustainability', and '#ecofriendly'. The function within Python that helped me pull those specific Tweets was `twint.config()`. In collaboration with my partner, Eduardo Gomez, we were able to take those Tweets and create a custom CSV file that was formatted in a way that would be able to work with the other parts of the program to pick up food entities. The food entity recognition model that is used in this research had been developed by previous students that were working on a different aspect of this project [16]. Each Tweet in the dataset consisted of the Tweet ID, date and time that the Tweet was made and sent, user ID, username, the Tweet, and the language that it was written in.

The previous study conducted by Chenze and Lee [16] to create the entity recognition algorithm utilized a publicly available collection of Tweets. The dataset is from 2009 and consists of 1.6 million Tweets [17]. The text content was obtained and analyzed throughout the duration of the training on the data through machine learning techniques. The attributes that were present for each record were as follows: a Tweet identification number, timestamp of Tweet creation, whether or not the data was queries, the user who posted the Tweet, and lastly, the text content of the Tweet itself. As mentioned before, only the text

content was used. The immense number of Tweets and the fact that the dataset includes Tweets that are both food and ones that are not related at all, allowed for the use of subsets in both training and validation sets in the model.

B. Instagram Dataset

The goal with Instagram was to analyze only images that were posted instead of captions. This allowed for variety in the research as the Twitter portion was all text-based analysis. In order to authentically analyze and display the sustainability information to users, I believed it was necessary to obtain a dataset that contained images directly from Instagram food bloggers. This study makes use of a dataset that Seungbae Kim has put together consisting of 33,935 Instagram influencers that are further categorized by types of influencers [18]. This included beauty, family, fashion, fitness, food, interior, pet, travel, and other. 300 posts were collected for each influencer totaling to 10,182,500 posts in the dataset.

This study focused on food influencers. Due to the immense number of posts provided, I decided to narrow down to 100 food influencers totaling 24,454 posts. From there a random sample of 25 images was taken and used as a subset to analyze the posts using Microsoft Computer Vision. Breaking down the dataset into a smaller sample allowed for me to analyze and understand the synergistic interaction of the computer vision software and the entity recognition algorithm in more depth. Additionally, another reason for a smaller sample being used was the fact that there was a restriction on the rate at which the Computer Vision could be run due to the pricing tier that was used. This limitation is explained in more detail in Section V.

C. FoodKeeper Dataset

Provided by the U.S. Department of Agriculture's Food Safety and Inspection Service, this dataset contains 509 unique foods, followed by their categories [19]. The dataset consists of several subpages within including Version, Category, Product, CookingTips, CookingMethods, and Data Dictionary. The version page states the latest changes and updates that are made to the current version of the FoodKeeper Dataset that the user is utilizing. Additionally, the category page focuses on the

categories that the food listed on the products page are broken down into, and selected categories have been further broken down to subcategories. Based on the product ID number, select foods have been given tips on how to properly cook them to ensure food safety which are located in the CookingTips page. Several metrics are listed in the CookingMethods page, where foods sorted by the product ID are given specific means of preparation for a proper outcome. An example of this may be, if a food item is to be grilled, then based on the weight of the item the appropriate time to cook would be listed. A data dictionary is provided to define terms within the dataset for the users to understand.

This study focuses on the product section, specifically the information that defines proper food storage by different means. Along with the tips and storage details, keywords that are affiliated with the food items are listed as well. The previous study conducted by Chenze and Lee [16] focused on the keywords to create an entity recognition algorithm, which is utilized within this study as well.

IV. APPROACH

As mentioned in Section I, I decided to take a look into both Twitter and Instagram and the possibility of utilizing both platforms in different ways to display sustainability messages. Twitter is a more text-based platform. With Tweets and the option to retweet, the platform is a means for people to post their thoughts and status updates. Considering the fact that Twitter started off as an SMS based platform [20], a character limit was imposed by carriers. Even when the platform was transferred over to a web-based platform, the limitation was kept as it aligned with the purpose and uniqueness of the brand. On the other hand, although Instagram incorporates several different features, users mainly associate and use the platform for images. There are many ways that videos and images can be posted on this platform including: stories, feed, reels, and IGTV. I decided it would be most accessible to work with images that are posted to the main feed, as that was the feature that this platform was originally popularized for. After realizing this, I believed it would be beneficial to analyze food related text from Twitter and analyze food related images from Instagram. This would provide more functionality to

the purpose of this project, and additionally add some variance in ways that the program can be altered.

A. Twitter

Fig. 1. Steps in the Twitter program pipeline.

Figure 1 provides a clear visual representation of the approach that was taken step by step in the program to produce the output as intended. Starting with the Live Streaming Tweets, which in this case was TWINT, in collaboration with my partner, we used the scraper to collect Tweets that would be put through data processing. The Tweets needed to be converted to a format that would be suitable for training. The function `preProcessLocal()` took in a Tweet as input and converted it to lowercase, replaced any username and URL with an empty string, and removed hashtags. The output is plain text and is ready to send off to the next function. This function was essential and used multiple times throughout the program to ensure that Tweets were being processed correctly. Those Tweets taken from the scraper were directed to a dataset which is used later in the program to identify entities and produce responses.

As mentioned before, this project incorporates the food entity recognition model [16] from previous research. The focus of the entity recognition model was to identify Tweets to train based on keywords found in the FoodKeeper dataset. Around 40,000 Tweets were identified and then trained in the model to create the Name entity recognizer. The processed data from TWINT and training data were both put towards the entity recognition model. Both were in .csv file format. From there the data was trained, and if Tweets from the dataset referenced food, the entity was returned.

Being able to Tweet back a relevant sustainability informational response warranted working with the FoodKeeper dataset and seeing the best way to formulate the response given the information in a certain format. Within the dataset, as described in section III, the sustainability information is broken down into three means of storage: pantry, refrigeration, and freezing. From there the information is further broken down into specifics such as date of perish for the item, specific tips on ways to store the item, or minimum and maximum recommended time in a given metric. Due to these specifications, it was crucial for me to take into consideration all of the various versions of tips that can be provided to a user and the specific format to display that information needed to be determined as well. This was taken into account in the `food_item_info.ipynb` Jupyter notebook.

In the `response.ipynb` Jupyter Notebook, Eduardo and I created reasonable responses for each scenario given the referenced food. The response was formulated in a way that was organized by each storage method. If there were multiple tips to be given for one method, for example pantry, then all of the tips related to how that item could be stored in the pantry, or the date of perish if stored in pantry were all outputted. This allowed for maximum functionality and ensured that we were providing as many options and safe food storage tips to avoid situations such as date label confusion. As mentioned in Section 1, date label confusion is a big contributing factor as to the reasoning why so many Americans prematurely discard food.

B. Instagram

Fig. 2. Steps in the Instagram program pipeline.

With Instagram, the approach was slightly different. I discovered Microsoft computer vision, which allowed for the images to be scanned and a result to be returned with a description of the image and the confidence level for the accuracy at which the artificial intelligence deemed appropriate. The response from Computer Vision is displayed and discussed further in Section V. At first, I had to take a look into the API to see what prerequisites were required of me in order to incorporate it into the program [21]. The first requirement was to have an Azure subscription and was able to create one for free through the student plan that they offer. That plan did come with some limitations that will be discussed later in Section V. The next requirement was to have Python 3.x and pip, preferably the latest version, installed on the machine. This was already done on my end because they were used in the work done for Twitter in some respects as well. Moreover, I found the last requirement very interesting. After getting the Azure subscription, I needed to create a resource within my portal to get a key and endpoint that it would deploy. That key and endpoint created within my resource is used to connect my application and the Computer Vision service.

Once those requirements were met, my next step was to look through the given code to see how this service in particular worked. Computer Vision provides code in various languages on how to use the service and the ways to tag and analyze an image. This project was programmed entirely in Python, so the version of Computer Vision I used was Python as well. The API has the ability to analyze both local and remote images. I first tested the code to make sure the foundation was working before I proceeded to test multiple food related local images at a time. The remote portion allows for a user to run the artificial intelligence API on images pulled from a specific URL. Once I got the remote portion of the analyzer compiling and running, I modified the code in order to analyze local images, since I knew that I would be working with a food images dataset which would be located on my device directly. From there, with the assistance of Dr. Anand Panangadan, we extracted the zipped images from the dataset I retrieved from Seungbae Kim as discussed in Section III. Once the random sample of images was chosen, the subset I was working with contained 25 images from the larger

influencer dataset. After this, I added all of the local image file name pathways in a list and ran them through Computer Vision to retrieve outputs of the image descriptions and confidence percentages of the subset. Those image descriptions were then added to a .txt text file which would then be the main dataset file that the entity recognition model would interact with to produce responses.

As displayed in Figure 2, the training model that was used within the program was the same as the one for the Twitter responses. The 40,000 Tweets were a good foundation as to the training model to be used in both instances of this project. One difference however was the fact that with the Instagram image description responses did not need to be pre-processed and altered as the Tweets did, since the text that Computer Vision outputs is lowercase with no characters that need to be eliminated. The food entity recognition model picked up the entities within the .txt and produced the responses using the same method as we formulated with the Twitter aspect of the project.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Twitter Responses

Fig. 3. Mock Tweet using Twitter API

My partner and I used the Twitter API with the baseline access we had to create a mock Tweet in order to see the accuracy of how the responses would be displayed. As seen in Figure 3, we created a profile through the API, and Tweeted out a message related to food storage. We made sure that there would be

hashtags and characters to see if `preProcessLocal()` would be able to take care of eliminating characters and processing plain text. We believed that visualizing the Tweets on the actual platform for us was an important research aim and objective and we wanted to be as true to the platform as we could.

```
i had this amazing watermelon FOOD for a snack today! i only ate half of it not sure what to do
with the rest 🍉

Total Entities found: (watermelon,)
=== watermelon ===
Pantry Tip: ['The Date of Perish for Watermelon is from 1 to 2 Days', 'A Watermelon tip about the Date of Perish is Or until ripe..']
Refrigerate Tip: ['The Date of Perish for Watermelon is from 3 to 4 Days']
Freeze Tip: ['Watermelon can be stored in the Freeze for 12 Months']
```

Fig. 4. Responses generated by the program

Figure 4 displayed the interaction between a Tweet, the food entity recognition model, described in the previous sections, and the responses that my partner and I formulated based on the data from the FoodKeeper dataset. As can be seen in this specific example, watermelon was the food related entity that the model recognized and identified. The entity that was found was then identified in the FoodKeeper dataset and food preservation tips were displayed to the user. This format is in list form, which retrieves the tips from the dataset without a paragraph or syntax. As mentioned previously, Eduardo and I created responses for scenarios that would display complete sentences. We believed it would look more professional and easier for users to understand. Additionally, it can be seen in the pantry section of the returned output that there is more than one pantry related tip, as mentioned earlier in Section IV, certain storage methods came with multiple tips.

Fig. 5. Response to user using Twitter API

Figure 5 displays the final response to the user in a response Tweet. The user that has Tweeted out the food related message is tagged, followed by the sustainability information from all three methods of storage to prevent premature perishing of food and to lower date label confusion. The Tweet is addressed from “USDA FoodKeeper Tips” since the source of the information comes from that specific dataset. This additionally allows for users to know that the information that they are receiving is verified by an established organization that has done their research to ensure accuracy in the information that they are providing to the public.

B. Twitter Limitations

As mentioned in Section IV, Twitter started off as a SMS based platform, which meant it was necessary to have a character limit. However, as it transitioned into a web-based platform, the character limit remained as part of the branding for the company. This also entailed a limit when it came to the responses we needed to output. With the 280 character limit, the question at hand was how would we be able to reasonably reply with a response in the case that it exceeded the limit? One possible solution is to count the characters in the response, and Tweet multiple replies to the user, breaking that response into different sections. That however comes with its downfalls, as it would not look professional and might be a hassle to separate the tips. This may also falter user attention, as it is more convenient to look at just one Tweet rather than two or more. A more reasonable solution, which would require further research, is to refine the responses the program outputs in a manner that includes the necessary tips only. There are multiple foods within the dataset that have sections without tips, as they are not applicable to them. An example is an item that can only be safe to freeze. Reasonably, that item would not have any pantry tips to provide. In the response, this would output “No Tip to give!” which in turn takes up characters where on the other hand, those characters could be better allocated to tips in the sections where there is information present.

Another limitation that comes with Twitter is that the version of the API that was being used did not allow for the response to be directly replied to the user. As seen in Figure 5, the version of the current program outputs a Tweet from a profile that tags the user who

Tweeted the food related item. The response is not directly replied to on the profile of the user. With further access to the Twitter API, which requires approval from the company, we would be able to have increased functionality where then we would have the option to reply directly to the Tweet that mentions the food entity.

C. Instagram Responses

Fig. 6. Instagram Post from @cookinmamas

Figure 6 displays one of the 25 images in the random sample dataset that was analyzed by Microsoft’s Computer Vision. As can be seen, it is a pizza with toppings.

Description of local image:
'a pizza with cheese and spinach' with confidence 46.48%

Fig. 7. Description of Figure 6 from Computer Vision

After running this image through the artificial intelligence API, we get Figure 7 as the description of the image. The confidence level at which the API is certain about its description is approximately 46.48%. The description is fairly descriptive and accurate with food related words present that will be picked up by the food entity recognition model.

```
a pizza FOOD with cheese FOOD and spinach

Total Entities found: (pizza, cheese)
pizza
['No Tip to give!']
['Pizza can be stored in the Refrigerate for 3 to 4 Days', 'A tip about Pizza is that Recommendation is for storage after cooking.']
['Pizza can be stored in the Freeze for 12 Months', 'A tip about P
izza is that Keep frozen. For safety, cook as directed.']
cheese
['No Tip to give!']
['The Date of Perish for Cheese is 6 Months', 'cheese can be store
d after opened in the Refrigerate for 3 to 4 Weeks']
['The Date of Perish for Cheese is 6 Months']
```

Fig. 8. Response output from program

In this situation, we had pizza and cheese picked up as food entities. Tips and sustainability information was returned for those two foods. It’s important to note that spinach was not picked up as a keyword. Further training of keywords and food related datasets would allow for more accurate results. In this research, the baseline for a true positive was that the food entity recognition model picks up at least one food within the description. In my research, the example from Figure 6 would be considered a true positive. Furthermore, since the Instagram portion of the project has more of a focus on the artificial intelligence API, I deemed the response being returned in the form of a list in the program to be sufficient for analysis.

D. Instagram Objective Evaluation

I conducted an objective evaluation for the Instagram posts descriptions and responses. For me this portion of the project came with the most variables and aspects that could be improved to better produce accurate output.

The first thing I did was to see the accuracy of the responses that Computer Vision outputted for the descriptions of the posts from the random sample set. In order to avoid any unconscious bias, I asked three of my colleagues, who were working on a different portion of related research, to take a survey. I compiled the 25 images into a folder and the responses from Computer Vision into an excel sheet and asked 3 participants to take the survey. The question that they were asked was “Does the description match what you see in the image?” The participants were asked to respond with a simple yes or no. Participant 1 stated that 22 out of the given 25 or 88% of the descriptions matched the Instagram post image. Participant 2 stated that 16 out of the given 25, in other words 64%, of descriptions matched the Instagram post in the sample dataset. Participant 3 agreed that 18 out of the 25 matched the description, which totals to 72%. The mean comes out to be approximately 74.67%. I also compiled a fourth excel that took the majority vote for each item. For instance, if two participants answered yes for one item, and the third answered no, the majority vote is yes. When doing so, I found that there was a mode of 16 out of the 25 items that were answered yes to descriptions matching the Instagram post. This comes out to be 64%. This number is decent, but definitely has much room for improvement. Future

work may include looking into ways to specialize or provide keywords to the Computer Vision API into looking at more specific details in an image.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{|E - T|}{|T|} \times 100 \\
 &= \frac{(14 - 25)}{|25|} \times 100 \\
 &= \frac{-11}{25} \times 100 \\
 &= -0.44 \times 100 \\
 &= -44\% \\
 &= 44\% \text{ error}
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 9. Percent Error Calculation [22]

Out of the 25 images in the random sample set, 14 had responses that were a true positive. This meant that at least one food entity was picked up in the description of the image, and a response was returned in regards to the food in the post. The percent error in this case totals to 44% as calculated in Figure 9. Since no entities were picked up at all, the blank descriptions are deemed as false negatives. It is clear that further training of the food entity recognition model is necessary for it to be able to pick up more of the food mentions in the Computer Vision descriptions.

Fig. 10. Example of False Positive

There were no false positives present specifically with the Instagram posts in the sample set. A false positive would result in the case that an entity was picked up that was not a food. An example, which was actually found when running the Twitter dataset, was the case of a rabbit as displayed in Figure 10. In some countries, rabbits are considered food, however this Tweet specifically was referring to the animal as a pet. Situations like these make us realize how important syntactical analysis and processing human language in the context of sentences is. As stated before, this would require further research which is possible in future work on this project.

E. Instagram Limitations

ComputerVisionErrorResponseException: (429) Requests to the Describe Image Operation under Computer Vision API (v3.2) have exceeded rate limit of your current ComputerVision F0 pricing tier. Please retry after 38 seconds. To increase your rate limit switch to a paid tier.

Fig. 11. Exception thrown by Computer Vision

One of the biggest limitations for Instagram was the version of the Azure subscription that I was utilizing. Due to the free pricing tier in the student plan, there was a limit as to the rate at which I could run images in the description operation from the API. Figure 11 portrays the exception that was thrown. There were three ways to bypass this limitation. The first was to upgrade to a paid tier. Another was to wait the allotted time to run the images again. The third and most effective solution I found was to run only a couple in the list at a time. Since there were a total of 25 images, I was analyzing from the food influencer dataset, I ran the first ten images in the list first, then ran the next ten images, and finally ran the last five images. By doing so I was able to meet the requirements of staying within the rate limit for the exception to not be thrown.

Fig. 12. Instagram post from @losangeles_eats

Description of local image:
'a plate of food' with confidence 49.22%

Fig. 13. Description of Figure from Computer Vision

Another limitation that I found within Microsoft Computer Vision was the accuracy and specificity of the descriptions of the images as discussed in the previous section as well. The intention for the responses was to give food sustainability tips. That is not possible if the description of the image is vague. An example of this can be found from running the Instagram post labeled as Figure 12. As displayed in Figure 13, the description that is returned by Computer

Vision is quite vague. If this response were to be run through the food entity recognition model, not entities would be determined, hence resulting in no response. Further research into Computer Vision and the API would be necessary to determine a solution as to the ways that this limitation could be resolved.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the correlation and relationship between food waste in the United States and social media is explored and analyzed. The two main platforms used in this research were Twitter and Instagram. Using a previously established food entity recognition model [16], mentions of food in Tweets and Instagram posts were recognized. Responses were formulated and sent that included tips and directions on how to store food appropriately to ensure food safety. The information was obtained from the USDA's FoodKeeper Dataset [19]. The aim is to combat Americans prematurely discarding food due to date label confusion.

It was found that with Twitter, sending responses was reasonable and possible through the help of the API. Through the use of Microsoft Computer Vision, Instagram posts were analyzed and described. Those descriptions allowed for mentions of food to be recognized and a response to be outputted. It was found that out of the sample set analyzed, 44% error was present when it comes to true positives in responses present in the output. A survey revealed that the mode of accuracy in which the Computer Vision API described the images in the sample set was 64%. Both platforms came with limitations, however with further research, can be resolved or minimized.

Future work can be conducted to further improve results and responses. Further access to Twitter's API would allow for us to reply to the user directly. Getting approval for access to this API takes time, however, is not impossible. Additionally, more Instagram post descriptions and Tweets can be used to train the food entity recognition model to cover more keywords which would improve entity recognition in mentions of food. Lastly, more analysis of Microsoft Computer Vision could be beneficial in narrowing down description results to more accurately display the contents of the image.

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PORTFOLIO

All of the code as part of the research for this project can be found:

<https://github.com/egomez3412/FoodKeeperResearch>

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